

PSYCHOLOGICAL MECHANISMS SHAPING SOCIAL- PSYCHOLOGICAL FACTORS IN BUSINESS LEADERSHIP ACTIVITIES

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12759138>

Annotation: In this article, the adaptation of internal psychological factors that ensure the effectiveness of entrepreneurial activity to specific social and psychological conditions, and their dependence on the individual's primary motivations, have been studied using scientific methods. Additionally, based on the aforementioned factors, the role of social psychology in studying the real psychological mechanisms of entrepreneurial motivation among today's youth is discussed.

Key words: psychology, entrepreneurship, business, market economy, management, leadership, personality, social responsibility, collaboration, interpersonal relationship.

Introduction

Today, developing the investment and export environment in our country, with a special focus on the economic sector, is an important task among the countries of the world. Therefore, President Shavkat Mirziyoyev paid special attention to the activities of entrepreneurs in the state program "Supporting Active Entrepreneurship, Innovative Ideas, and Technologies" [1]. In this context, the essence of an entrepreneur's activity in a market economy is also explained by criteria such as their mastery of the art of managing interpersonal relationships, organizing people into teams, planning and overseeing tasks, exchanging information, and responsibly coordinating these processes. Also, the intellectual potential and resourcefulness of entrepreneurs, their ability to meet the material and spiritual needs of people, and their deep sense of responsibility and duty towards their group, team, and society hold significant importance. The most essential trait required of every entrepreneur is the responsibility for interpersonal relationships. This involves establishing good relations with subordinates and partners and creating a healthy psychological environment to enhance the efficiency of production within the enterprise [2].

Discussion

Social and psychological factors play an important role in the activities of business leaders. These factors are of great importance in ensuring leadership processes and business success, and it is necessary for leaders to understand

and manage them. In particular, in the course of business activity, special attention should be paid to the following functions:

1. Leadership Styles: Entrepreneurial leaders use different leadership styles. These methods can change depending on the personality of the leader, the characteristics of the workers and the state of the enterprise. Effective leadership style depends on the leader's ability to motivate the team, guide them towards the goal and solve problems.

2. Team Building: Social and psychological factors are important in the process of team building. In order to build an effective team, leaders must know their employees well, know their strengths and weaknesses, and assign them appropriate tasks. It is necessary to create an atmosphere of trust, cooperation and mutual respect in the team.

3. Motivation and Support: Motivating and supporting employees is one of the important tasks of a business leader. Understanding the needs of employees, creating opportunities for them to develop and recognizing their successes will increase their productivity.

4. Communication and Interaction: Effective communication is of great importance in strengthening the relationship between the leader and the workers. Open and direct communication increases employees' trust in the leader and allows problems to be identified and resolved quickly.

5. Stress Management: Stress is common in the business world, and business leaders need to know how to manage stress. To reduce stress, managers can create a supportive environment for workers, provide opportunities for relaxation, and provide stress management training.

6. Social Responsibility: It is necessary for business leaders to remember their social responsibility towards society. This includes, in particular, considering the impact of the company's activities on the environment, society, and employees. Focusing on social responsibility increases the authority of leaders and strengthens their relationship with society [3].

Taking into account these factors, entrepreneurial leaders can effectively manage their activities and develop a successful business.

Acquiring positive content of the socio-psychological characteristics characteristic of managers is an achievement not only of leaders, but also of society. Today's demand is for leaders to be spiritual, cultured, skillful, capable, steadfast, and have perfect willpower [4]. Of course, having the mentioned qualities is very beneficial. Being able to use them appropriately creates a foundation for positive team dynamics and a healthy psychological environment.

In turn, this positively influences mutual relationships and enhances respect for the leader and their authority.

Results

The authority of a leader is expressed through every action and activity, signifying that the authority of the staff is a subject of steadfast determination. It fosters a sense of collaboration in interpersonal relations, creates conditions for accurate perceptions of individuals, and shapes an individual style. Additionally, reputation serves as a factor in the efficiency of production, stemming from the department of spiritual wealth and functioning as a mechanism for fostering a warm psychological environment.

The following requirements are imposed on a person's will:

- embodiment of will power;
- striving for the goal and keeping pace with the hardships of management;
- initiative, independence, creativity;
- courage, courage, not giving in to obstacles;
- self-restraint, self-restraint;
- discipline, self-reliance [5].

These requirements serve as the foundation for the efficiency of subjective activity and the creation of a warm psychological environment, akin to a tariff. This is because a sense of duty, responsibility, and self-confidence increases in tandem with an individual's commitment to their work. These qualities manifest differently in various leaders. In the field of management psychology, efforts focus on bringing out and developing such qualities and approaches. As previously mentioned, incorporating psychological knowledge and conditions as primary factors is advantageous for the management process and relationships between managers and employees. Scientific justification is sought through socio-psychological methods within management psychology [6].

Conclusion

In conclusion, it is imperative for leaders to develop each of the abilities, qualities, and characteristics mentioned earlier, foster alignment with the work team, and demonstrate empathy towards their concerns. As these qualities become more ingrained in the leader, they foster a healthier social and psychological environment within the team, enabling the avoidance of conflicts and effective management of stressful situations. Consequently, these conditions enhance labor productivity and efficiency, instill a sense of confidence in the

team members regarding the future, promote team cohesion, and mitigate negative phenomena such as work alienation.

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